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Policy Brief: Governance Pathways for the EU Soil Monitoring Law – A Perspective for Germany and the EU

This policy brief is based on findings from the German research programme “Soil as a Sustainable Resource for the Bioeconomy – BonaRes”, which was funded by the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTR). It is intended to serve as a guide for policy makers in the EU and Germany on the implications of the recently adopted EU Soil Monitoring Law (2025). Drawing on research from BonaRes, the policy brief outlines strategic reform pathways and concrete actions to improve soil policy implementation, strengthen institutional coherence and align soil governance with broader sustainability goals.

SOILS UNDER PRESSURE – POLITICAL INVISIBILITY AND THE PROMISE OF EU REFORM

Soils are the basis for important ecosystem services such as water regulation, nutrient cycling, biodiversity conservation and carbon storage (McBratney et al., 2014). Yet across Europe, these vital functions remain undervalued and poorly protected. Soil degradation caused by sealing, erosion, compaction and unsustainable management continues largely unchecked, posing direct risks to climate mitigation, food systems and biodiversity (IPBES, 2018). This degradation is not only an environmental issue, but also a political one: soil has long lacked a strong lobby and robust legal status.

This is gradually changing at EU level with the initiative ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ (European Commission, 2024), which aims to protect and restore soils in the EU and promote sustainable use. Specifically, this programme aims to halt soil degradation, preserve carbon stocks in the soil, curb soil sealing, reduce soil pollution and strengthen soil knowledge in society and politics.

The adoption of the EU Soil Monitoring Law in October 2025 could mark another turning point in European soil governance, depending on how effectively it is implemented and to what extent scientific knowledge is integrated into its design and execution. For the first time, a legal framework obligates Member States to define soil health standards and to establish national monitoring infrastructures within three years (European Commission, 2025). Soil health is thereby framed as the ability to continuously provide ecosystem services. Although the directive is conceptually significant, it lacks binding targets and enforcement mechanisms, which has led to criticism from civil society. The European Environmental Bureau (EEB) argues that compliance with the law is at risk if more robust metrics and thresholds are not established (EEB, 2025). The ‘EU Soil Strategy for 2030’ could remedy this situation (European Commission, 2021).

Resistance also comes from farmers’ associations such as the German Farmers’ Association (DBV) and the Bavarian Farmers’ Association (BBV), which cite excessive bureaucracy and fear that soils will be incorrectly classified according to rigid criteria (BBV, 2025). These controversies underscore the fragmented understanding of soil governance across different sectors and the lack of a shared vision for the importance of soils. Against this backdrop, the results of the BonaRes research programme argue for a new narrative framework: soils must be understood as multifunctional systems that are central to ecological resilience, rather than being treated merely as marginal resources or carbon accounting units. Both ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ and the ‘EU Soil Strategy for 2030’ appear to be initiatives towards such a narrative, although their legal anchoring in the Soil Monitoring Directive only partially reflects these priorities.

SOIL GOVERNANCE IN TRANSITION – CHALLENGES, REFORM PATHWAYS, AND POLICY LEVERS

The implementation of the 2025 EU directive occurs within a fragmented and weakly enforced governance environment. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) provides limited soil-specific incentives, and unlike air or water, soil still lacks a dedicated EU directive (Ronchi et al., 2019). In Germany, the Federal Soil Protection Act (BBodSchG) is widely regarded as outdated, as it focuses primarily on the remediation of contaminated sites and does not sufficiently address agricultural or ecological soil functions (BMUV, 2022). An amendment to the BBodSchG, which is to focus more on preventive soil protection, is currently under discussion.

Building on the governance disruptions framework (Schröter-Schlaack and Hansjürgens, 2019) and its application to German agricultural soil policy (Bartkowski et al., 2021), we identify three systemic challenges: inconsistencies between individual policy areas, insufficient use of monitoring data, and limited stakeholder participation. In addition, there are isolated administrative responsibilities and a lack of institutional learning between science, policy and practice. Although there are pilot innovations, such as modelled soil assessments, they remain outside of regular governance.

To turn this legislative moment into transformative action, five key reform pathways are recommended:

Policy Coherence and Institutional Design: Future EU soil policy should take the form of a Soil Framework Directive, aligning soil objectives with the European Green Deal, the EU Biodiversity Strategy and CAP Strategic Plans. At the national level, Germany must revise the BBodSchG to reflect soil governance and inter-ministerial cooperation. Stronger legal mandates and cross-sectoral structures are needed to ensure that soil is systematically included into spatial planning and sustainability strategies. Policy documents specifying implementation strategies are essential to complement the Soil Monitoring Law and BBodSchG.

Monitoring Infrastructure and Functional Indicators: The 2025 directive mandates harmonized

soil indicators, including biological activity, organic carbon and pollution levels (European Commission, 2025). These must be operationalized through adaptable, regionally contextualized monitoring systems. Germany's Soil Monitoring Network (BDF) should be aligned with EU platforms like LUCAS and Copernicus and transferred to a more comprehensive monitoring system. These systems should also allow real-time data access and integrate modern digital tools for dynamic decision-making.

Result-Based and Adaptive Policy Instruments:

Conventional payments for agri-environmental measures lack impact. Result-based agri-environmental schemes, possibly model-based (Bartkowski et al., 2021b), rewarding ecosystem services like water retention or increased organic matter, offer a more effective alternative. Carbon farming should be communicated as an integrated strategy that promotes climate protection, climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation. Result-based payments should be coupled with advisory services and risk-mitigation tools to facilitate uptake of soil-friendly management across diverse farming systems.

Stakeholder Participation and Regional Foresight:

The directive emphasizes inclusive governance and stakeholder participation in the design of national soil strategies (European Commission, 2025). This should be strengthened through regional stakeholder platforms, participatory foresight methods and scenario planning. These instruments can be used to tailor soil strategies to local conditions and increase their legitimacy. Institutional support for these platforms is essential to transform participation from symbolic consultation into genuine co-determination.

Communication and Societal Re-evaluation: Effective soil governance begins with public recognition and shared narratives. In recent years, the "Soil Security Frame" has been widely promoted in social science and environmental governance research to elevate the political visibility of soils, primarily by linking them to food security, climate mitigation and ecosystem services (McBratney et al., 2014; Baveye et al., 2016). While this framing has gained traction, it remains technocratic and tends to overlook the

cultural, ecological and societal dimensions of soils. In contrast, the “Soil Appreciation Frame” developed by the BonaRes programme emphasizes soils as multifunctional systems that are foundational to sustainability and long-term resilience. Elements of this narrative can already be found implicitly in the EU Soil Mission and in the draft amendment to the BBSchG. To anchor this broader perspective, value-based communication, inclusive dialogue and education are essential. Public campaigns should highlight not only the utility, but also the intrinsic value of soils as the basis of life for landscapes, ecosystems and intergenerational well-being.

OUTLOOK

The 2025 EU Soil Monitoring Law has opened a policy window for redefining how Europe treats its soil resources. However, legal requirements alone will not halt degradation or strengthen resilience. The long-term impact depends on how effectively politics, science and practice can agree on a common vision of soil as a public good. The reform paths outlined in this policy brief show that instruments and concepts already exist in the European research and policy landscape. What we need now are coordinated measures, political will and institutional learning. With sustained support, Europe has the opportunity to lead a new era of soil stewardship – from the ground up.

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